

Grief Reactions of Potential Organ Donors' Bereaved Relatives: An Observational Study

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: Most of the families of potential donors experience the death of their relatives in the context of an Intensive Care Unit. While under a great emotional impact, bereaved relatives must make a decision that will condition the life of other patients. A better understanding of grieving within donation contexts will help ICU staff to better support families during this process.

OBJECTIVES: To empirically describe the emotional reactions of families of potential organ donors in the face of the death of a loved one; to analyze the relationship of these reactions with factors that concur in the process of sickness/death.

METHODS: Prospective observational study in 16 Spanish hospitals over a 36-month period. Data of 421 families of potential donors were collected through a previously validated instrument, including: relatives' emotional responses, deceased's and relatives' characteristics; circumstances of death, and behavior of health staff.

RESULTS: Unexpected deaths are linked to a more intense emotional reaction and less acceptance of death than anticipated deaths. Additional stressors, such as perception of poor treatment by hospital staff, deficient medical care, and bad relationships within the family itself are associated with more exacerbated reactions.

CONCLUSION: Observation and analysis of the considered factors may contribute to anticipating the emotional reactions of bereaved relatives and lead to better support during the grieving process, increasing the family's well-being and facilitating a better informed organ donation decision.

SUMMARY OF KEY POINTS

- The consideration of some basic indicators of the process of evolution and death of potential donors can help staff of the Intensive Care Units to anticipate the emotional reactions that family members will experience when facing the death of their loved one.
- Intensive Care Unit staff should provide special support in the grieving process to families of potential donors who experience unexpected deaths with little time to evolve, especially those that involve children and young people.
- The perception of the health workers' treatment and medical care by family members of potential donors can be an important factor in the emergence of different emotional reactions to the death of the loved one, complicating the process of grief when the perception is negative.
- The existence of a bad climate of family relations can favour the emergence of extreme emotional reactions and anger in relatives of potential donors when faced with the death of a loved one.

INTRODUCTION

The families of potential organ donors play a decisive role in the transplant system because organ procurement organizations require family consent as a pre-requisite for deceased organ donation in the majority of western countries¹⁻². Bereaved relatives of potential donors must therefore make a decision that will condition the life and health of other patients at a critical time, when they are under a great emotional impact³⁻⁴. One of the major factors in family decision is the way they deal with the emotional experience of the loss of the loved one. Thus, donation refusal occurs to a greater extent in situations where the death and its circumstances overwhelm the relatives' cognitive and emotional resources⁵⁻⁷. Refusal of consent is an important barrier to organ donation. Its percentage varies widely in different international contexts, yielding in 2017 values of 13.0% in Spain, 28.7% in Italy, 35.2% in the UK, 41.3% in Australia, or 72.9% in Turkey⁸.

Although donations derived from circulatory death are steadily increasing, to date, brain-stem death has comprised the largest pool of potential donors in all countries⁸ (Council of Europe & ONT, 2018). This implies that most of the families of potential donors experience the death of their relative in the context of admittance in an Intensive Care Unit (ICU). The families of patients admitted to ICUs frequently suffer critical states of depression, anxiety, and post-traumatic stress disorders when receiving the communication of the death⁹⁻¹¹. Different processes play an important role in the emergence and evolution of these states. Pre-existing factors such as the family's support network and previous stress and bereavement experiences may condition family bereavement¹²⁻¹⁴. Likewise, the care and support received from health professionals in the ICUs play a decisive role: inadequate support can lead to worsening of the grieving process *in situ*¹⁵⁻¹⁷ and adversely affect the families' subsequent grieving evolution^{4,18,19}.

However, good support can help to improve the crisis of the acceptance of the death²⁰⁻²².

The literature on organ donation provides substantive and qualitative descriptions of the emotions experienced by families of potential donors and of the analysis of their relationship with the decision to donate^{4, 5, 7, 23}. However, the systematic analysis of the factors that condition these emotional reactions has received less attention. Hence, very few studies have quantitatively explored the relationship between the emotional reactions of potential donors' relatives and the different factors concurring in the process of sickness and death; in some works, these relationships have only been analyzed indirectly²⁴⁻²⁶. Similarly, the existing studies include mainly the families that grant permission, and few studies contemplate both donor families and families that refuse consent⁵. It is therefore necessary to gain empirical knowledge of the factors that modulate the emotional experience of the families of potential donors.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Relatives' emotional reactions to the communication of death are conceptualized as indicators of the initiation of the grieving process, considering grief as the physiological, psychological, and social reaction produced by the loss of the loved one^{12,27}. These reactions show how family members cope with the challenge of death and are the result of personal, family, social, and situational factors^{12, 17, 27, 28}. However, grief experience is a more complex process that may run a number of possible courses depending on factors such as cultural and family pressure, individuals' developmental history, the nature of the relationship with the deceased, and the quality of support from significant others^{12,29}. In accordance with the most current models, it is assumed that the course of the grieving process does not correspond to completing a series of phases, as proposed by the traditional models; on the contrary, people can take different paths

that include complex and ambivalent emotions²⁹⁻³¹. Therefore, the present study includes all the possible emotional reactions present in the bereaved relatives, considering such reactions as multiple and diverse.

OBJECTIVES

Taking into account the previous considerations, the objectives of this work are: 1) to describe the patterns of emotional reaction of the families of potential organ donors to the communication of their relative's demise; 2) to analyze the relationship of different emotional reactions with diverse factors that concur in the process of sickness and death. A better understanding of grieving within donation contexts will help the ICU staff to better support families during this process, fulfilling the dual purpose of promoting greater well-being of the bereaved relatives and increasing the donation rate.

METHODS

Study design

A quantitative, cross-sectional, observational study was developed.

Setting

The study was carried out in Spain, which has been leading the international donation rates for decades⁸ and is acknowledged as a referent in transplant coordination practices³². Sixteen hospitals participated in the study.

Sample

A random proportional sampling procedure was applied to select 36 hospitals from the existing Spanish hospitals with potential organ donation activity. The average donation rate was used as the sampling criterion. Of the pre-selected hospitals, 16 agreed to participate in data collection. The participating hospitals belonged to seven Autonomous Regions of Spain. Over a 36-month period, the transplant coordination

teams from the participating hospitals collected data from 421 families of potential donors. Of them, 338 (80.3%) derived in consent to donate, whereas the other cases refused permission.

Instrument and variables

A data collection instrument designed and validated in a previous study²⁵ was used. The previous content validation process included the following procedures: review and integration of instruments in use in different hospitals and institutions; consultation with transplant coordinators, regional coordinating bodies, and those responsible for national transplant coordination; and pilot study with a reduced sample.

The instrument included open- and closed-ended items about bereaved relatives' characteristics and different factors involved in family bereavement and decision process. Each family is considered as a single case. However, the instrument requires the registration of the specific family members who participated in each interview process. It also requires the registration of all emotional reactions that emerged in the family group, which could differ from one member to another. The work that is presented herein focuses on the description of the emotional reactions of the relatives of potential donors and their relationship with various factors that concur in the process of sickness and death. The relationships between the different factors and family decision to donate have been analyzed elsewhere²⁶. Table 1 presents a detailed description of the items that were included for analysis in the present study and the response options for each item. The complete original instrument that was applied for the global study can be found in the Supplementary Material.

INSERT TABLE 1

Procedure

The members of the research team provided written instructions for the participating

coordinators and explained the data collection procedure to them by telephone to resolve any possible doubts. The research team instructed the coordinators to collect data during the process of approaching and interviewing the relatives in all cases of donation request, regardless of whether or not other factors subsequently led to donation. Transplant coordinators registered the data on a printed questionnaire for each interview. Upon completion, the questionnaires were sent to the research team for review and analysis. No identification data about the deceased or the relatives were sent to the research team.

Method of Analysis

Descriptive, univariate and multivariate exploratory analyses were performed by means of the IBM®-SPSS® package. Specific analyses are detailed in each section.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The study design had received ethical approval of the committee of the academic institution involved (***) and was approved by the Spanish Sanitary Research Fund of the Spanish Ministry of Health and Consumer Affairs (FIS Ref 95/538). The study procedure was designed in agreement with the Spanish National Procurement Organization (ONT).

RESULTS

Descriptive analysis

Table 2 presents the family members' observed emotional reactions, which were collected by means of non-exclusive categories. In this sense, different emotional reactions could be observed simultaneously in different family members.

INSERT TABLE 2

Table 3 presents the absolute and relative frequencies of the different indicators collected. The sample presents an important diversity of situations, which reflect death

by different causes, different age ranges, and different evolution times of the illness.

INSERT TABLE 3

Exploratory analysis

In order to achieve a global view of the relationships between relatives' emotional reactions and the factors involved in the relative's death process, Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA)³³ was applied. MCA is an analysis technique for nominal categorical data that can be used to detect and represent underlying structures or relationships in a complex data structure. MCA represents categories of the considered variables in a graphical bi-dimensional space that summarizes joint relationships among them.

All the variables described above were included except for the occurrence of suicide, because its low frequency would distort the graphical results. MCA was performed by means of the Optimal Scaling algorithm included in the IBM®-SPSS® package. Figure 1 summarizes the main results of MCA. Categories that are close to each other tend to be associated more frequently. In turn, categories located close to the axis intersection include a greater number of cases. In order to make Figure 1 conceptually clearer, the categories were structured across two different dimensions.

INSERT FIGURE 1

The dimension, "Age of the deceased" structures the situations that correspond to the different age groups of the deceased relatives. The older groups are on the left, and the younger groups are on the right. The categories referring to the cause of death and the relatives involved are structured consistently according to the age of the deceased throughout this dimension. Thus, cerebrovascular accidents appear more closely related to categories representing the higher age of the deceased, expansive processes are located in the area of intermediate age, and cerebral anoxia and traumatic brain injuries are located

close to the groups of younger deceased people. The involvement of son/s or daughter/s, the partner, and other people is also linked to the older deceased groups, whereas the involvement of parents is associated with the groups of younger deceased people.

The dimension, "Acceptance-Anger" traces a continuum between the situations with the most emotional disturbance, which are located at the upper end, and the situations in which acceptance of death/resignation occurs, which are located at the lower end, leaving the situations of sadness and controlled crying in the intermediate space. The proximity in the graph of the emotional reactions of anger-aggression, intense crying and screaming, and denial of death indicates that they tend to occur together. Similarly, the proximity of these reactions to the diagnostic category of circulatory death indicates their association in our data. The fact that the two dimensions are oblique to each other indicates that emotional reactions are related to the age of the deceased. In this sense, intense emotional reactions would be more frequent when the deceased patient is younger, whereas the reactions of families who have lost older loved ones tend to be more restrained and nearer to acceptance.

Situations in which family relations are rated as poor or regular, situations of sudden death with a hospital stay before death of less than 6 hours, and situations of families whose socio-cultural level was estimated as low or medium/low appear close to the pole of intense emotional reactions and, especially, to reactions of immobility/mutism. The chart also shows that situations in which complaints about health care or personal treatment are expressed are linked to intense emotional reactions; both types of complaints tend to be associated with each other. The health staff's interventions do not present a clear association with the emotional reactions, as they are placed at the mid-point of the dimensions, although they are closer to the circumstances in which sadness and controlled crying appear. They are, however, associated to a greater extent with

reactions of acceptance/resignation after a long stay in the hospital before death, with family relations rated as good, and with family socio-cultural level estimated as high or medium/high. Although with a weaker association, the family's expression of satisfaction with the personal treatment and medical care received is also more closely related to acceptance/resignation.

In order to systematically evaluate the relationships suggested in the MCA, contrast tests were carried out between each of the emotional reactions and the different concurrent factors. The crosstabs procedure was used with the calculation of the Likelihood Ratio as the contrast statistic, and the estimation of p , using the exact Monte Carlo method, which avoids errors due to tables with disperse or asymmetric cells. The adjusted standardized residuals (ASR) test was also used to show whether certain emotional reactions are more (ASR > 1.96, $p < .05$) or less frequent (ASR < -1.96, $p < .05$) when certain categories of the indicators occur. The results are presented in Tables 4 and 5.

INSERT TABLES 4 AND 5

DISCUSSION

This study represents the first work that prospectively and quantitatively analyzes the global relationship between the emotional responses of relatives of potential donors and different factors that concur in the process of illness/accident and death of their loved one.

The results show a coherent pattern of association between the different emotional reactions and the set of factors analyzed, which are synthesized and interpreted in Figure 2. In accordance with the current literature, our data reflect that grief is a complex process that can include different emotional reactions that are not exclusive³⁰. In the light of the current work, these reactions do not imply a sequence of phases through which family members must necessarily pass²⁹⁻³¹. However, they do represent different degrees of emotional distress and/or acceptance of death that condition the ability of family members to become aware of the situation created by

the death and to respond to the requests made of them³⁴.

INSERT FIGURE 2

The observed relationships are consistent with the theoretical proposals analyzing the factors that affect people's capacity to cope with highly stressful events, both in general and in the case of the death of a relative. In this sense, the degree of the frustration of expectations, the lack of resources to deal with the situation, and the existence of additional stressors all contribute to explain the emergence of more intense emotional reactions^{30,34}. In the case of grief, these situations produce what Stroebe and Schut³⁵ conceptualize as *overload* in the families, and are linked to a greater difficulty to accept the reality of the relative's death and to face the demands it entails³⁴⁻³⁶. Thus, in this study, the most exacerbated emotional reactions are associated with factors that reflect the frustration of one's life project: the death of a child, a teenager, or a young person; the subsequent involvement of the parents; and causes of death such as traumatic brain injury or the occurrence of suicide. Unexpected deaths have been frequently associated in the literature with more complicated grieving processes³⁷⁻³⁸. In these situations, the feeling of sadness is linked to other emotional reactions such as anger³⁰, as reflected in our results. In the specific case of death by suicide, the data presented show greater frequency of denial of death and of anger and uncontrolled crying, in accordance with feelings of guilt, blame, and confusion that are attributed to this situation³⁹. As other works have suggested, the lack of resources - such as time in cases of sudden death - that emerges in the donation context prevents anticipatory grief and contributes to intense emotional reactions⁴⁰. This fact is reflected in cases with very short hospital stays before the death. A low socio-cultural level, associated in our results with more intense reactions, would also contribute to a lower capacity to process the complex events undergone by the family³⁴. Finally, the existence of additional stressors would favor the development of more complicated grieving

processes. In this sense, our results are associated with intense emotional reactions—including angry responses—in cases in which the relatives had a negative perception of the personal treatment and medical care received. This relationship has already been suggested by numerous works in the specific field of donation^{5,41,42}. This additional stress could contribute to conflictive family relationships, which are related herein to reactions such as anger-aggression or uncontrolled crying and which emerge as complicated grieving factors in the literature²⁹. The more intense emotional reactions in mothers compared to fathers found in our results is related to the differentially assigned gender roles of emotional expression in western contexts, which inhibit men's expression of sadness⁴³.

The reverse of these situations is found in those cases of death in which the family has had time to anticipate the loss and, in the words of Stroebe and Schut⁴⁴, to initiate *loss-oriented activities*. These cases are reflected in this study in longer hospital stays and in situations of vascular-cerebral accidents in adults and older people. The existence of good family relations, which herein appears associated with better acceptance of the death, would help to buffer the effects of the loss, as other works in the field of donation have shown^{12, 45,46}.

LIMITATIONS

This study has focused on the prospective collection of indicators directly observable by health personnel in the interaction with bereaved relatives. It does not address the analysis of other factors that may condition the grieving process, such as those referring to personal variables and cognitive or emotional states not expressed by family members. Results should therefore be complemented with studies that collect these aspects, usually retrospectively.

On the other hand, although a previously validated instrument based on observable indicators was used, some

variables may be influenced by the subjective judgment of transplant coordinators. This is the case of the attributed socio-economic level and the perceived relational climate within the family. Therefore, the results referring to these variables should be analyzed with caution and in the context of their relationship with the other variables. The possible limitations arising from the performance of multiple comparisons and the commission of Type 1 errors have been addressed through the use of robust statistics (Likelihood Ratio, Monte Carlo estimation), the exact presentation of the effect size, the examination of residuals, and the performance of global analyses (MCA).

CONCLUSIONS

The observation and analysis of factors that concur in the process of illness/accident and death of potential donors contribute to understanding and anticipating bereaved families' emotional reactions to the death of a relative. Unexpected deaths within short evolutionary times that frustrate life expectancy are linked to more intense emotional reactions and less acceptance of death. Additional stressors, such as the perception of deficient personal treatment or poor medical care and the existence of bad relationships among family members, are also associated with more exacerbated reactions that hinder dealing with the emotional and cognitive demands of the loved one's death. The ICU staff should pay special attention to anticipate and adequately address these situations and thus promote the well-being of the families and their ability to decide with some perspective about the altruistic behavior of donating.

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Table 1. Items considered in the final instrument and derived variables

ITEM/VARIABLE	RESPONSE OPTIONS
EMOTIONAL RESPONSES OF RELATIVES AT DEATH COMMUNICATION (Non-exclusive)	
Immobility or silence	[Yes] - [No]
Sadness or controlled crying	[Yes] - [No]
No emotional expression	[Yes] - [No]
Denial of the death	[Yes] - [No]
Intense crying-screaming	[Yes] - [No]
Anger or aggression	[Yes] - [No]
Acceptance of the death—resignation	[Yes] - [No]
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DECEASED	
Sex	[Male] - [Female]
Age	[Years]
CIRCUMSTANCES OF DEATH	
Stay in hospital before death*	[Hours]
Cause of death*	[Traumatic brain injury] - [Cerebrovascular Accident] - [Expansive process] - [Others]
Case of suicide	[Yes] - [No]
CHARACTERISTICS OF BEREAVED RELATIVES	
Attributed socio-cultural level	[High] - [Middle] - [Low]
Family relations perceived by coordinator	[Good] - [Regular] - [Poor]
Kinship of relatives participating in initial request interview	[Father]-[Mother]-[Partner]-[Son/s/Daughter/s]-[Sibling/s]-[Other relative/s]- [Other persons]
BELIEFS AND EXPRESSIONS OF BEREAVED RELATIVES	
Family expressed satisfaction with the medical attention	[Complained] - [No Comment]-[Expressed satisfaction]
Family expressed satisfaction with personal treatment received	[Complained] - [No Comment]-[Expressed satisfaction]
BEHAVIOUR OF HEALTH AND COORDINATION STAFF	
Provided progressive and continuous information on patient's condition	[Yes] - [No]
Allowed flexible visiting hours	[Yes] - [No]
Same person always dealt with family	[Yes] - [No]
* The instrument included an open-ended question that was subsequently categorised	

Table 2 Emotional reactions of family members of potential donors at the time of death communication

		Count	Column %
Denial of Death	Yes	55	13.6
	No	349	86.4
Uncontrolled Crying-Screaming	Yes	45	11.1
	No	359	88.9
Anger-Aggression	Yes	26	6.4
	No	378	93.6
Immobility-Mutism	Yes	31	7.7
	No	373	92.3
Sadness-controlled crying	Yes	214	53.0
	No	190	47.0
Acceptance of death-resignation	Yes	223	55.2
	No	181	44.8
No emotional expression	Yes	33	8.2
	No	371	91.8

Table 3 Occurrence of different concurrent indicators in the process of death of potential donors

			Count	Column %	
Characteristics of the deceased	Sex of the deceased	Male	266	63.3	
		Female	154	36.7	
	Age	<1 year	0	.0	
		1-12	11	2.6	
		13-15	6	1.4	
		16-25	52	12.5	
		26-35	51	12.2	
		36-45	78	18.7	
		46-55	87	20.9	
		56-65	77	18.5	
		66-75	53	12.7	
>76		2	.5		
Circumstances of death	Stay in the hospital before death	<6 hours	11	2.7	
		6-12 hours	35	8.5	
		13-24 hours	123	29.7	
		25-47 hours	24	5.8	
		48-71 hours	87	21.0	
		72-95 hours	31	7.5	
		96-119 hours	25	6.0	
		120-240 hours	62	15.0	
		>240 hours	16	3.9	
	Cause of death	Traumatic brain injury	134	32.1	
		Cerebrovascular accident	241	57.7	
		Cerebral anoxia	31	7.4	
		Expansive processes	4	1.0	
		Other	8	1.9	
	Suicide	No	414	99.3	
		Yes	3	.7	
	Death Statement	Circulatory death	409	97.4	
		Brain-stem death	11	2.6	
	Family characteristics	Socio-cultural level of decision-makers	Low	89	21.5
Low-medium			48	11.6	
Medium			201	48.6	
Medium-high			29	7.0	
High			47	11.4	
Relatives involved		Father	No	326	77.4
			Yes	95	22.6
		Mother	No	295	70.1
			Yes	126	29.9
		Sibling/s	Yes	167	39.7
			No	254	60.3
		Son/Daughter/s	Yes	179	42.5
			No	242	57.5
	Partner	Yes	223	53.0	
		No	198	47.0	
Other	Yes	120	28.5		

			Count	Column %
	relative/s	No	301	71.5
	Other	Yes	13	3.1
	person/s	No	408	96.9
Family Relationships		Good	350	83.9
		Regular	54	12.9
		Bad	13	3.1
Relatives' beliefs and expressions of satisfaction/complaints	Personal Treatment received at the hospital	Complaints	22	5.3
		Satisfaction	141	33.7
		Did not express any	255	61.0
	Medical attention	Complaints	23	5.5
		Satisfaction	171	40.9
		Did not express any	224	53.6
Health staff interventions	Provided progressive and continuous information on patient's condition	No	190	45.5
		Yes	228	54.5
	The same person always dealt with the family	No	199	47.6
		Yes	219	52.4
	Flexible visiting schedule	No	212	50.7
		Yes	206	49.3

Table 4. Relations of the emotional reactions of the bereaved relatives of potential donors with concurrent factors (I)

Emotional reaction	Variables/Categories with which the emotional reaction is associated
Denial of Death	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Related to the age of the deceased (LR = 18.44, p = .018): more frequent in deceased of 36-45 years (ASR = 2.9) and less in deceased of 66-75 years (ASR = -2.2) • More frequent in hospital stays of less than 6 hours before death. (ASR = 2.2) • Less frequent in CVA situations (ASR = -2.1) • Related to cases of suicide (LR = 12.1, p = .002): more frequent in cases of suicide (ASR = 4.4) • Related to the socio-cultural level of the family (LR = 12.5, p = .017): more frequent in socio-cultural level rated as low/medium (ASR = 2.0) and less frequent in level rated as high (ASR = -2.4). • Related to the involvement of the mother (LR = 7.6, p = .006), more frequent when the mother is involved (ASR = 2.9) • Related to sons/daughters/s' involvement (LR = 12.4, p = .15): more frequent when sons/daughters/are not involved (ASR = -2.5) • Related to family relationships (LR = 8.9, p = .011): more frequent if they are rated as regular (ASR = 2.5) and less frequent if they are rated as good (ASR = -3.2). • Related to the same person always dealing with the family (LR = 5.2, p = .029): more frequent when the same person dealt with the family (ASR = 2.2).
Disconsolate crying-screaming	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less frequent if the deceased was in the age range of 66-75 years (ASR = -2.3). • Related to prior hospital stay (LR = 19.3, p = .018): more frequent in stays of less than 6 hours (ASR = 2.7) and 13-24 hours (ASR = 2.4), less frequent in intervals of 48-71 hours (ASR = -2.2) • Related to cases of suicide (LR = 14.0, p = .003), more frequent in suicide situations (ASR = 4.9) • More frequent when family relationships are rated as bad (ASR = 2.3) and less frequent when rated as good (ASR = 2.0). • Related to satisfaction with the personal treatment received in the hospital (LR 8.0, p = .21): less frequent when satisfaction with treatment is expressed (ASR = -2.4).
Anger-aggression	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More frequent when the age of the deceased is in the range of 1 to 12 years (ASR = -3.1). • Related to prior hospital stay (LR = 18.9, p = .21): more frequent in stays of 6 to 12 hours (ASR = 2.3) and less frequent in stays of 120-240 hours (ASR = -2.4). • Related to cases of suicide (LR = 7.0, p = .024), more frequent when suicide occurs (ASR = 4.3). • Related to family's perceived socio-cultural level (LR = 18.1, p = .002): more frequent in families perceived with low socio-cultural level (ASR = 3.1) • Related to family relationship assessment (LR = 12.8, p = .001): more frequent when family reactions were rated as regular (ASR = 2.2).

Emotional reaction	Variables/Categories with which the emotional reaction is associated
	<p>= 4.2) and less frequent when rated as good (ASR = -3.9).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Related to the satisfaction with the personal treatment received in the hospital (LR = 18.9, $p < .001$): more frequent when the family expressed complaints (ASR = 5.1) and less frequent when they expressed satisfaction (ASR = -2.5). • Related to satisfaction with medical care received (LR = 34.137, $p < .001$): more frequent when family expressed complaints (ASR = 7.6) and less frequent when they expressed satisfaction (ASR = -3.1).
Abbreviations:	
LR: Likelihood Ratio	
ASR: Adjusted Standardized Residual	

Table 5. Relations of the emotional reactions of the bereaved relatives of potential donors with concurrent factors (II)

Emotional reaction	Variables/Categories with which emotional reaction is associated
Immobility-Mutism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More frequent when the deceased was in the age range of 16 to 25 years (ASR = 2.0). • More frequent when the family expressed complaints about the personal treatment received (ASR = 2.0) • Related to the same person always dealing with the family (LR = 4.4, p = .041): less frequent when it was not the same person (ASR = 2.1).
Sadness-controlled crying	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Related to the socio-cultural level (LR = 9.6, p = .042); more frequent when socio-cultural level was rated as low-medium • Related to the father's involvement (LR = 5.1, p = .031): more frequent when the father participates (ASR = 2.2) • Related to the mother's involvement (LR = 6.4, p = .012): more frequent when the mother participates (ASR = 2.5) (ASR = 2.2) • Related to facilitating a flexible visiting schedule (LR = 10.4, p = .001): more frequent when it is provided (ASR = 3.2)
Acceptance of death/resignation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Related to the sex of the deceased (LR = 4.4, p = .039), more frequent when the deceased is a male (ASR = 2.1). • Related to the age of the deceased (LR 24.6, p = .002): less frequent when the deceased was in the age range of 16 to 25 years (ASR = -3.1) and more frequent when he or she was in the range of 46-55 (ASR = 2.1) and 66-75 (ASR = 2.2) • Related to the socio-cultural level perceived in the relatives (LR = 11.3, p = .024): less frequent in low socio-economic levels (ASR = -2.5). • Related to the father's intervention (LR = 12.4, p<.001): less frequent when the father intervened (ASR = -3.5). • Related to the mother's intervention (LR = 12.6, p<.001): less frequent when the mother intervened (ASR = -3.5). • Related to the perception of family relationships (LR = 10.7, p = .005): more frequent when family relationships were rated as good (ASR = 3.0) and less frequent when rated as regular (ASR = -2.0) or bad (ASR = -2.4). • Related to the comments about the personal treatment received at the hospital (LR = 8.9, p = .014): less frequent when there were complaints about treatment (ASR = -2.9) • Less frequent when there were complaints about medical care (ASR = -2.2).
No emotional expression	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less frequent when the age range of the deceased was from 13 to 15 years (ASR = -2.7) • Related to the father's involvement (LR = 6.6, p = .017): less

frequent when the father intervened (ASR = -2.3)

- Related to the mothers 's involvement (LR = 11.4, p = .001): less frequent when the mother intervened (ASR = -3.0)
- More frequent in family relationships rated as regular (ASR = 2.1).

Abbreviations:

LR: Likelihood Ratio

ASR: Adjusted Standardized Residual

FIGURE-2

FAMILIAS DONANTES

Este cuestionario pretende recoger información sobre diversos aspectos de la entrevista familiar. Por favor, rellénelo en caso de que la familia haya concedido el permiso de extracción. El cuestionario está confeccionado en dos hojas autocopiables y lleva adherido un sobre pre-franqueado. Una vez cumplimentado, sepáre el sobre y envíe dentro de sí la hoja superior del cuestionario, denominada "Ejemplar para el envío". La hoja inferior, "Ejemplar para la coordinación", quedará para su propio registro.

Todos los datos serán considerados como estrictamente confidenciales y se procesarán a nivel global. Si tiene alguna duda o sugerencia puede ponerse en contacto con el equipo de investigación de la U.A.M. a través del teléfono (91) 397-52-18 o el fax (91) 397-52-15.

MUCHAS GRACIAS POR SU COLABORACIÓN

IV. CARACTERÍSTICAS DE LOS DECISORES PRINCIPALES

Parentesco: Nivel cultural: Nivel socio-económico: Edad aproximada (Alto-Medio-Bajo) (Alto-Medio-Bajo) (Alto-Medio-Bajo) (Alto-Medio-Bajo)

Actitud personal hacia la donación (Favorable-Desf.)

I. CARACTERÍSTICAS DEL FALLECIDO

Fecha de la entrevista: / / Sexo: Varón Mujer

II. CIRCUNSTANCIAS DEL FALLECIMIENTO

Tiempo de estancia previa en el hospital: Causa del fallecimiento:

Tipo de potencial donante: En muerte cerebral A corazón parado

Caso judicial: SI NO

III. CARACTERÍSTICAS DE LA FAMILIA

Personas presentes en la entrevista de petición inicial:

Número: Parentesco: Familiares muy allegados Otros familiares Otras personas (especificar)

Población de residencia de la familia:

¿Pertenece la familia o el fallecido a algún grupo étnico minoritario? No SI ¿A cuál?

¿Profesaba alguna religión... el fallecido?

No SI ¿Cuál? No sabe

En relación al trato personal recibido en el hospital, la familia... ¿manifestó quejas... manifestó satisfacción... no se manifestó?

...manifestó quejas ...manifestó satisfacción ...no se manifestó

En relación a la atención médica recibida, la familia... ¿manifestó quejas... manifestó satisfacción... no se manifestó?

...manifestó quejas ...manifestó satisfacción ...no se manifestó

¿Cómo calificaría las relaciones existentes entre los miembros de la familia?

Buenos Regulares Malas

Señale si la familia conoció, personalmente o por referencia, a alguna persona... ¿resplandeciente... en dialisis o lista de espera... familiar de donante

SI NO NO sabe SI NO NO sabe SI NO NO sabe

VII. PROBLEMAS MENCIONADOS POR LOS FAMILIARES

Señale cuáles de estos problemas ha mencionado la familia antes de conceder el permiso.

Dudas sobre la muerte del familiar Ausencia de los decisores principales Problemas con la apariencia o integridad del cadáver Falta de respeto en el trato al difunto Problemas religiosos Deseo de llevarse a casa Desconfianza sobre el destino de los órganos Queja por el trato personal recibido en el hospital Queja por la atención médica recibida Resentimiento social/venganza Desacuerdo entre los miembros de la familia Miedo a la opinión de otros familiares o conocidos Desconocimiento de la voluntad del fallecido Negativa expresada en vida por el fallecido Otros (especificar)

VIII. ARGUMENTOS UTILIZADOS

A continuación se muestran argumentos que pueden utilizarse para inclinar a la familia a la donación.

1.º Señale los argumentos que se utilizaron más (M) o si desconoce su efecto (D). 2.º Valore, la eficacia de cada argumento utilizado, señalando si fue eficaz (S), ineficaz (N) o si desconoce su efecto (D).

	Se utilizó	Fue eficaz
Ensayamiento de la generosidad del difunto	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ensayamiento de la generosidad de la familia	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Oportunidad de "dar vida" o aliviar el sufrimiento a varias personas	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Enfatizar que muy pocas familias tienen la oportunidad de donar	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Possibilidad de evitar que otras familias pasen lo que ellos están pasando	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Señalar que ellos también podrían necesitar algún día	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Possibilidad de sacar algo positivo de la muerte	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Possibilidad de que "algo" de su familia siga vivo	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Consejo que representa la donación para las familias de los donantes	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Positivo recuerdo del difunto por una última buena obra	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Positiva valoración que da la sociedad a la donación y el trasplante	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Apoyo que las distintas religiones dan a la donación	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Describir a un potencial receptor que despierte la simpatía de la familia	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Comparar las consecuencias del "sí" y del "no" para los pacientes en espera	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Responsabilizar a la familia del destino de los pacientes en espera	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Existencia de una "urgencia cero"	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Hacer ver que se desperdiciarán los órganos si no se aprovechan	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Señalar que las familias que no donan suelen arrepentirse de su decisión	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Asunción del coste de los gastos básicos de enterramiento	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Necesidad de realizar, en cualquier caso, la autopsia	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Otros (especificar)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

OBSERVACIONES:

¿Podría enviarse a alguna persona de la familia, desde la Coordinación de Trasplantes de su hospital, el cuestionario para participar en el estudio? SI NO

En caso afirmativo, puede anotar en este espacio, para su posterior utilización, los datos de la persona más adecuada para recibir el cuestionario.

Nombre: Calle/Plaza: Población: Código postal: Parentesco con el fallecido: N.º: Piso:

IX. ESTRATEGIAS UTILIZADAS

Señale cuáles de las siguientes estrategias se utilizaron para facilitar la obtención del permiso:

Informar progresiva y continuamente de la evolución del familiar Mantener siempre a la misma persona en el trato con la familia Facilitar que la familia se "desplaza" del fallecido Facilitar un horario flexible de visitas Limitar el número de familiares presentes en la entrevista de petición Seleccionar a familiares concretos para mantener la entrevista Informar personalmente sobre la donación a todos los familiares allegados Dar tiempo a la familia para que desahogue sus sentimientos Dar tiempo a la familia para que hable sobre el difunto Mostrarse afectado por el sufrimiento de los familiares Separar y vencer aisladamente a los miembros relictivos de la familia Inducir una respuesta rápida de los familiares a la petición Hacer ver que no existe prisa para tomar la decisión Asilar a los familiares del entorno general del hospital durante la decisión Utilizar el apoyo de personas cercanas a la familia

X. VALORACIÓN DE LAS RAZONES DEL PERMISO

¿En qué medida cree que han influido los siguientes aspectos en la obtención del permiso?

	Familia mucho	Familia bastante	No ha influido	Difícil
Trato recibido en el hospital	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Atención médica recibida	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forma de comunicar el fallecimiento	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Momento de solicitar la donación	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Argumentos utilizados al solicitar la donación	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Relación establecida entre coordinador y familia	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Actitud previa de la familia hacia la donación	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Nivel cultural de la familia	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Relaciones entre los miembros de la familia	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Creencias religiosas de la familia	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Desconocimiento de la voluntad del difunto	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Conocimiento de la voluntad del difunto	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Conocimiento de pacientes trasplantados	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Conocimiento de pacientes en lista de espera	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Otros relevantes (especificar)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

XI. ÓRGANOS DONADOS POR LA FAMILIA

¿Se ha negado la familia a donar algún órgano en concreto?

No SI ¿Cuál? Corneas Corazón Otros

